

ENGAGEMENT OF ARMED POLICE FORCE, NEPAL IN COMMUNITY-BASED DISASTER MANAGEMENT

A Thesis

Submitted to the

Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Tribhuvan

University, in Partial Fulfillment for the Post Graduate Diploma Degree

in Security and Disaster Management Studies

Submitted by:

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Batch No. 2080/081

APF Command and Staff College

Sanogaucharan, Kathmandu, Nepal

July 2024

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DECLARATION

I, SURENDRA BHADUR SHAHI, declare that this thesis entitled “ENGAGEMENT OF ARMED POLICE FORCE, NEPAL IN COMMUNITY-BASED DISASTER MANAGEMENT”, submitted to Department of Humanities and Social Sciences, Tribhuvan University is my original work unless otherwise indicated or acknowledged in the thesis. The thesis does not contain materials that have been accepted or submitted for any other degree at the University or other institution. All sources of information have been specifically acknowledged by reference to the authors and institutions.

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LETTER OF RECOMMENDATION

This thesis entitled “ENGAGEMENT OF ARMEDPOLICE FORCE, NEPAL IN COMMUNITY-BASED DISASTER MANAGEMENT”, has been prepared by Mr. SURENDRA BAHADUR SHAHI under my guidance and supervision. I, hereby, recommend it in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the Degree of **POST GRADUATE DIPLOMA** in Security and Disaster Management Studies for final examination.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Ganesh Dhungana', is written over a horizontal line.

Thesis Supervisor

M.Phil. Ganesh Dhungana

Harvard Humanitarian Initiative, Staff

July 01, 2024

APPROVAL SHEET

We certify that this thesis entitled “ENGAGEMENT OF ARMED POLICE FORCE, NEPAL IN COMMUNITY-BASED DISASTER MANAGEMENT”, submitted by Mr. SURENDRA BHAHDUR SHAHI to Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Tribhuvan University, in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the Degree of POST GRADUATE DIPLOMA IN SECURITY AND DISASTER MANAGEMENT STUDIES has been found satisfactory in scope and quality. Therefore, we accept this thesis as a part of the said degree.

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This research study is not the result of a single effort of the researcher but the combined efforts of many people without whom it would have been impossible to accomplish this research. While exploring this thesis, I got constructive and insightful academic assistance from professors, people, and the Armed Police Force, Nepal organization.

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study is to analyse various community-based disaster management initiatives carried out by Armed Police Force, Nepal. It is engaging in various community-based disaster risk reduction activities through awareness sessions, and capacity-building building programs through lectures, practical exercises, seminars, pamphlets, social media platforms, and workshops. Guiding by the National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act 2017, the Armed Police Force, Nepal has disseminated knowledge proactively about disaster risks and preparedness to a broad spectrum of the community, including students. The research employs a qualitative method, combining primary and secondary data. For the primary data collection 5 key informant interviews have been taken from Armed Police Force, Nepal. The findings reveal that the APF, Nepal has conducted comprehensive capacity-building training sessions covering critical areas such as collapsed structure search and rescue, swift water search and rescue, deep diving, firefighting, dead body management, medical first response, and rope rescue. These trainings have further prepared participants to provide immediate engagement in community-level disasters. APF, Nepal's commitment to community-based disaster management also includes collaborative exercises with community members, students, and other agencies fostering the exchange of resources and knowledge to empower local communities. In conclusion, initiatives of APF, Nepal in community-based disaster management have yielded successful outcomes, characterized by improved disaster management protocols and effective rescue missions. Collaborating with local communities and organizations has established strong partnerships, laying the foundation for future coordination and collaboration, thereby enhancing overall disaster preparedness and response.

Keywords: APF, Nepal, disaster management, community-based disaster management, disaster risk reduction

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronyms / Abbreviations	Full form
APF, Nepal	Armed Police Force, Nepal
CBDM	Community Based Disaster Management
CBDRR	Community Based Disaster Risk Reduction
CCR	Cable Car Rescue
CSSR	Collapsed Structure Search and Rescue
DBM	Dead Body Management
DM	Disaster Management
DMTS	Disaster Management Training School
DRRM	Disaster Risk Reduction and Management
DRRSPA	Disaster Risk Reduction Strategic Plan of Action
EWS	Early Warning System
GLOF	Glacier Lakes Out-burst Flood
INSARAG	International Search and Rescue Advisory Group
KII	Key Informant Interview
LAPA	Local Adaptation Program of Action
LGO	Local Government Operation
MFR	Medical First Responder
NAPA	National Adaptation Program of Action
NPDRR	National Policy on Disaster Risk Reduction
NRRS	National Risk Reduction Strategy
PPE	Personal Protective Equipments
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SFDRR	Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction
SWSS	Swift Water Search and Rescue
VDMC	Village Disaster Management Committee

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The fragile geology and steep topography have made Nepal the 20th topmost disaster-prone country in the world. Among 200 countries, Nepal ranks 4th, 11th, and 30th in relative vulnerability to climate change, earthquake, and flood hazards, respectively (*Ministry of Home Affairs*, 2023). Nepal's geographical positioning renders it vulnerable to various natural disasters, including earthquakes, fire, drought, epidemics, storm hailstorms, avalanches, Glacier Lake Out-Burst Flood (GLOF), floods, and landslides (Dixit, 2003). He adds further that, there has been an increase in disasters over the past 20 years due to its geography. Community-based institutions and organisations such as local government, community neighbourhoods and international organisations have been recognized as important elements in Disaster Management (DM) (Hakaloba et al., 2016).

A global discourse is about whether the community can be resilient to climatic threats, Stern (2007) notes the need for a shift in international policy on low-cost adaptation technology and Community Based Disaster Management (CBDM) approach instead of a mitigation approach. The mitigation approach is promising but may not provide instant resilience to the community. Therefore, low-cost adaptation technology and the CBDM approach have become popular globally.

CBDM initiates a process involving sequential stages that can be operationalized to reduce disaster risk. The processes of CBDM are guided by principles of subsidiarity, economies of scale, equity, heterogeneity, and public accountability (Quader et al., 2023). Moreover, the different stages in CBDM are disaster vulnerability risk assessment, risk reduction planning, early warning systems, post-disaster relief, and participatory monitoring and evaluation (Bhagat, 2014).

Notably, CBDM is a popular approach for collective action against unpredictable natural hazards and for minimizing socio-economic losses in Nepal, particularly in the rural areas because the National Adaptation Program of Action (NAPA) and Local Adaptation Program of Action (LAPA) are not being game changers yet with poor connectivity, and poor governance. At first, it was used in Nepal during the great earthquake of above 8 rector scale

in 1934 (Rafferty, 2024). Therefore, in Nepal, the Early Warning System (EWS) and preparedness are major strategies for Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) and LAPA employing the local community.

The group primarily collects early warning information and signals for the community for preparedness, along with rescue, assistance, and reconstruction and recovery, thus diminishing susceptibility (Bista, 2023). Similarly, Zhang et al. (2013) claim it is an indigenous people's perception of disaster risk reduction. In summary, the local community's capacity enables them to be proactive, as noted by (Victoria, 2002) who highlights six key features: local grassroots involvement, importance for the most vulnerable groups and the public, specific public threat reduction, recognized capabilities and management tools, integrity between development and disaster risk reduction, and facilitation of the role of outsiders.

Security forces are actively engaged in rescue and relief activities in different parts of the world. Although, the primary task is to maintain peace and security, especially in the wake of disaster security forces intervene to assist society (Raj, 2008). So, in the context of the Nepal, Armed Police Force (APF), Nepal has been engaging in the DM field since its establishment. The engagement of the APF, Nepal, in community-based disaster management is a critical component of the country's overall disaster preparedness and response strategy.

CBDM emphasizes the active participation of local communities in all phases of disaster management, from preparedness to recovery, fostering resilience and self-reliance (Shaw, 2012). The International Conference of Hyogo Framework for Action (18-22 January 2005) delivered the message to the world that disaster is a global agenda that needs to state every component to get involved in dealing with (Zhou et al., 2014). Therefore, the APF, Nepal with its extensive reach and capabilities, plays a pivotal role in this process by collaborating with local communities, providing training, and facilitating resource mobilization.

The APF, in Nepal holds significant importance in upholding peace, stability, and border protection, all of which are essential components of disaster preparedness and effective governance (Khatri, 2020). This study explores the different initiatives taken by APF, Nepal in CBDM, highlighting the wide range of disaster management activities in the local community.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

CBDM is the approach that seeks the wide participation of the local community employing Indigenous knowledge and local resources in various programs such as awareness, educational programs, training, simulation activities, etc., for effective DM (Lassa et al., 2018). Since its establishment, APF, Nepal has been deploying in all phases of disaster, especially in search and rescue operations. APF, Nepal is conducting various community empowerment programs that coordinate with the local community and other government and non-government agencies in the DM field. The literature in the fields of CBDM acknowledges that the community themselves are the first responder in any disaster; their role and involvement play a crucial role in saving lives and the loss of property during a disaster. Moreover, their role plays a significant role in reducing and managing disaster risk as well. Security forces are well organized, readily available, and trained manpower so they can play a vital role in disaster preparedness and mitigation.

However, there are various regulations, provisions, and mechanisms related to DM in Nepal, but there is ambiguity even though security agencies are assigned the role of DM, including their other regular roles and responsibilities, without providing adequate financial resources and specific legal mandates (Paudel, 2023). Despite the increasing occurrence and intensity of disasters, CBDM continues to be a relatively unexplored domain in terms of assessing the effectiveness of various organizational involvements (Pandey, 2019). Moreover, there is little research or literature on how APF, Nepal, is contributing to CBDM through different initiatives to reduce disaster risk and effective response during disasters. Therefore, this study describes the organizational involvement of APF, Nepal, in CBDM activities through different initiatives.

1.3 Research Question

The study aims to answer the following research question.

How is APF, Nepal, contributing to CBDM through its different initiatives?

1.4 Objective of the Study

APF, Nepal conducts various activities to empower the local community in disaster preparedness and response endeavours. Therefore, the general objective is to discuss different

CBDM initiatives of APF, Nepal to promote CBDM and empower the local community. The specific objective of this study is to analyse different kinds of CBDM initiatives carried out by APF, Nepal.

1.5 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.1

Conceptual framework of the study.

1.6 Significance of the Study

Nepal, being highly prone to various natural disasters like earthquakes, floods, and landslides, requires well-developed strategies for managing disasters. The crucial involvement of the APF, Nepal in addressing these emergencies by delivering awareness programs and capacity development activities to ensure the safety of the community is noteworthy. Examining their

participation in CBDM has the potential to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of disaster response initiatives (Tiwari & Rayamajhi, 2018).

The engagement of APF, Nepal in CBDM is crucial for building and providing operational support to the community in the DM phase, especially in preparedness and response. This research can identify the strengths and gaps present in prevailing practices, providing suggestions for improvement. Moreover, an analysis of the involvement of APF, Nepal in CBDM contributes value to wider dialogues concerning the interaction between civil and military entities and the functions of security forces in humanitarian efforts. This study is significant to understanding the CBDM initiatives of APF, Nepal, by different actives to prepare a more resilient and prepared community capable of effectively managing and mitigating disaster impacts.

1.7 Scope and Limitation of the Study

This study is focused on the engagement of APF, Nepal in CBDM activities by analysing different initiatives that support the preparedness and response phases of the DM cycle. For this study, the KIIs are limited in numbers due to time and resources limitations. The conclusion drawn from this study may not cover the ultimate solutions to manage disasters all the time rather, it can contribute some knowledge on it. Moreover, as times have changed and several activities APF, Nepal may conduct in the future, the result might be different. This study is entirely focused on the general activities conducted by APF, Nepal, to enhance the capacity of local people to respond to disasters effectively.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

This chapter includes the DM introduction and the disaster cycle. Moreover, it describes the CBDM with the help of existing and published journals, books, online resources, etc. This chapter also includes the legal framework and the role of APF, Nepal, in the disaster field.

2.1 Disaster Management

DM involves both normal mode, planning and mitigation, and crisis mode, emergency response and recovery to avoid and reduce the probability of a crisis (Lan, 2002). Likewise, Bly et al. (2021), also advocate in the same way, as DM involves planning, preparation, mitigation, response, and recovery to effectively manage serious events that threaten health, life, and property. Furthermore, emphasizes DM is all about reducing risk and exposure to hazards (i.e. mitigation) planning and preparing for upcoming hazards and preventing a disaster (i.e. preparedness), reducing impacts of disaster through effective response effort, and search and rescue (i.e. response) and restoration through clean-up and reconstruction (i.e. recovery) (Poser & Dransch, 2010).

Therefore, DM is managing all the risks, effects, and impacts, ensures safety, and facilitates swift recovery through assessment, planning, resource allocation, and coordination among agencies in all phases of disaster i.e. preparedness, mitigation, response, and recovery, from natural or human-made disasters.

2.1.1 Disaster Management Cycle

Figure 2.1

Disaster Management Cycle

Source: Asian Disaster Risk Reduction Centre, 2005

According to Andrews (2002) multifaceted approach is engaged DM, which involves the development of disaster preparedness systems utilizing real-time monitoring engines and storage processing modules to efficiently restore data. Scholarly research underscores that preparedness is a complex concept encompassing various factors necessitating tailored attention and resources for successful implementation (Kirschenbaum, 2002). Countries in Latin America and the Caribbean have transitioned towards institutional preparedness and disaster prevention, underscoring the significance of coordination, planning, training, and logistics in the preparedness process (Poncelet & Goyet, 1996). Moreover, contemporary disaster preparedness systems can exploit personal electronic devices and forecast data to ascertain and carry out preparatory measures for individuals at risk of disasters, thereby enhancing overall readiness and response capabilities (Benssam et al., 2016).

Disaster response constitutes a crucial element within the realm of emergency management, encompassing the orchestration of diverse agencies, institutions, and individuals to efficiently alleviate the consequences of either natural or anthropogenic disasters. The preparatory, warning, emergency, rehabilitation, and reconstruction stages serve as indispensable constituents of the disaster response framework. Proficient disaster response necessitates meticulous foresight, explicit assignment of duties, and institutionalized channels for communication and collaboration (Kahn & Barondess, 2008). Disasters have the potential to result in extensive human, material, economic, and environmental damages that surpass the capacity of impacted communities to manage through their internal resources (Bradley et al., 2016).

The phase of recovery in DM is a pivotal stage that ensues the initial response to a disaster. During this phase, the attention transitions from addressing the immediate requirements of impacted communities to the restoration of normalcy, reconstruction of infrastructure, and mitigating the enduring consequences of the incident (Jouannic et al., 2016). Moreover, (Rani et al., 2017) state that the recovery stage within the realm of DM plays a pivotal role as a fundamental element of the holistic strategy aimed at mitigating the impact of either naturally occurring or man-made catastrophic occurrences. This particular stage involves the reconstruction of crucial services, the rebuilding of impaired physical structures, and the execution of tactics to enhance the resilience of impacted societies.

The mitigation phase within the realm of DM is significantly impactful in reducing the consequences of disasters on both human life and property, serving as a cornerstone for

subsequent phases (Tay et al., 2022). Efficiently addressing risks through mitigation necessitates the identification of predominant risks and the execution of suitable strategies throughout the DM cycle stages, encompassing preparedness, response, recovery, and mitigation (Miranda et al., 2022).

Moreover, Eden and Gonzalez (2023) define the effectiveness of mitigation endeavours as hinges on the engagement of proficient individuals and influential figures to promptly formulate transparent and pertinent risk evaluation and mitigation strategies, taking into account systemic risks within an interconnected global landscape. Furthermore, community-centered initiatives and efforts by state and federal agencies are indispensable elements of disaster mitigation, underscoring the significance of engaging diverse stakeholders and establishing sustainable mitigation plans (Ciottone & Gougelet, 2024).

2.2 Community-Based Disaster Management- Theoretical Approach

Most disaster response can be characterized as a command-and-control structure one that is top-down and with a logistic centre approach. Because of this, we observe a lack of community participation that results in failures in meeting the appropriate and vital humanitarian needs, unnecessary increases in requirements for external resources, and general dissatisfaction over performance despite the use of exceptional management measures (Sadiqi et al., 2015).

Moreover, Joseph et al. (2020) explain that by recognizing these limitations, the CBDM approach promotes a bottom-up approach working in harmony with the top-down approach to address the challenges and difficulties. To be effective, local communities must be supported in analysing their hazardous conditions, vulnerabilities, and capacities as they see themselves.

The CBDM approach represents a foundational method of enhancing community empowerment and serves as a persuasive tool for facilitating the dissemination of concepts and assertions from grassroots levels. It focuses on building the capacities of people and communities in four key aspects: disaster prevention and mitigation and disaster preparedness, emergency response, and recovery and rehabilitation. CBDM strives to mitigate the effects and vulnerabilities of disasters by engaging communities in a manner that prioritizes individuals within the realm of advancement (Luna, 2013).

Furthermore, Kumar (2023) defines a process aimed at enhancing the community's ability and resilience to effectively handle different hazards, thereby integrating hazard management

practices into their daily routines. Moreover, he further defines that, the key elements of CBDM as encompassing the formulation of a Village Disaster Management (VDMC) Plan when focusing on a specific community unit where the community itself ensures ownership and reflects local conditions. So, the plan should be prepared using the participatory approach based on facilitation provided by experts.

To mitigate the effects and vulnerabilities, according to Mohammad & Huq (2016), the government by itself is insufficient and incapable of effectively managing and addressing all categories of disasters through its mechanisms without active engagement from the populace of any given nation, a widely accepted concept put forth by policymakers, experts, and professionals. The shortcomings of the top-down approach to DM in reducing disaster risks serve as clear evidence of this assertion. Consequently, a multitude of academics and stakeholders think that the time has come to embrace a fresh strategy that incorporates vulnerable individuals directly into the formulation and execution of measures for mitigation, preparedness, response, and recovery, as communities are most adept at evaluating their susceptibility and are best positioned to make decisions that safeguard their welfare.

United Nations Development Program (UNDP) Report 2002-2009 states that DM covers a broad range of interventions undertaken before, during, and after a disaster to prevent or minimize loss of life and property, minimize human suffering, and hasten recovery. The management of a disaster can be viewed as a series of phases which includes the response and relief phase, recovery phase, prevention phase, mitigation phase, and preparedness phase (United Nations Development Program, 2002). Moreover, it has identified eight good practices in community-based disaster risk management which are as follows:

Table 2.1

Good Practices in Community-Based Disaster Risk Management

S.N.	Contents	Remarks
1.	Awareness Generations	Sharing the Word, spreading the knowledge
2.	Capacity Building	Empowering the communities, making them independent
3.	Institutionalisation	Laying the foundation stone for a better tomorrow
4.	Involvement of Community	A step towards sustainability: of the people, for the people

5. Gender Mainstreaming Empowering women
 6. Convergence and United we stand
Partnerships
 7. From the Field
 8. Moments of Triumph
-

Source: United Nations Development Program, 2024

As the government of Nepal ensures the framework of CBDM, it has tried to institutionalize it through acts, regulations, policies, and guidelines which are: Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Act 2017, DRRM Regulations 2019, National Risk Reduction Strategy (NRR) 2009, Disaster Risk Reduction Strategic Plan of Action (DRRSPA) 2018-2030, Local Government Operation (LGO) Act 2018, National Policy on Disaster Risk Reduction (NPDR) 2018, etc. Moreover, there is a focus on the involvement of the local community as they are the first responder during disasters. Therefore, involving communities in the realm of DM has formalized the informal survival tactics at the community level, allowing residents to respond to emergencies without relying on external assistance from governmental bodies or non-governmental organizations. The main aim of this DM approach rooted in communities is to transform vulnerable communities into resilient ones (Kafle, 2012).

CBDM is a widely embraced strategy for coordinated efforts against unforeseeable disasters and for reducing socio-economic impacts in Nepal, especially in rural regions due to the limited effectiveness of the National Adaptation Program of Action (NAPA) and Local Adaptation Program of Action (LAPA) in the presence of inadequate infrastructure and governance that lacks implementation and empowerment of local community especially, in DM. Initially introduced in Nepal following the significant earthquake measuring above 8 on the Richter scale in 1934 (Rafferty, 2024).

Furthermore, Bista (2022), clarifies that disaster represents a phenomenon that is characterized by both unpredictability and predictability, it is a prevalent issue that results in undesirable negative externalities and significant social costs for both communities and individual households. In this context, the adoption of CBDM groups, along with their focus on adaptation and collective action, emerges as a viable and indeed essential approach to addressing disasters through a combination of adaptive strategies and mitigative measures aimed at diminishing the adverse externalities and social costs associated with such events. Consequently, the presence

and active engagement of CBDM groups in adaptation and collective action activities play a crucial role in effectively managing disasters.

CBDM aims to empower the local community on a sustainable basis. Moreover, Pandey and Okazaki (2005), interpret that the fundamental component of sustainable DM involves the engagement of communities in such endeavours. Among the prevailing aspects of community participation are collaboration, involvement, empowerment, and ownership among the local populace. The primary focus of DM initiatives should be directed towards communities and their inhabitants. Without the sustainability of DM initiatives at both individual and community levels, the mitigation of losses and the extent of calamities becomes challenging. An avenue must exist an avenue for individuals to participate right from the inception phase of DM activities.

2.2.1 Disaster Awareness

Awareness programs play a crucial role in addressing various issues in the community. These initiatives commonly involve a mixture of strategies, including counselling, education, and community mobilization efforts aimed at enhancing public understanding and participation (Weno et al., 2020).

Awareness initiatives aim to inform members of the community regarding the specific risks and dangers prevalent in their locality. This acquired knowledge empowers individuals to implement proactive measures to mitigate these risks. For instance, communities situated in areas prone to earthquakes can familiarize themselves with constructing earthquake-resistant buildings and formulating emergency strategies (Lindell et al., 2016). Moreover, (Shiwaku & Shaw, 2008) highlights the importance of awareness in the community as awareness of DM in schools and communities is critical for mitigating the adverse impacts of natural and man-made disasters. Educating individuals on disaster preparedness ensures that students, teachers, and community members are equipped with the knowledge and skills necessary to respond effectively during emergencies. For instance, schools that integrate disaster preparedness into their curriculum foster a culture of safety and resilience among students. This proactive approach not only safeguards life but also minimizes the disruption to education caused by disasters.

Effective DM relies heavily on comprehensive awareness programs that employ various methods to disseminate crucial information. Workshops and training sessions are fundamental

as they provide hands-on experience and interactive learning opportunities, enabling participants to practice skills such as first aid, evacuation procedures, and emergency response (Paton, 2003).

CBDM initiatives are indispensable in providing individuals with the necessary expertise and understanding to react effectively in emergencies. The significance of emergency response methods, initial medical assistance, fire prevention, earthquake preparedness, and flood prevention initiatives are paramount in this context. Through the education of community members in emergency response strategies, communities can enhance their readiness to promptly and effectively respond during calamities, thereby diminishing the likelihood of injuries and fatalities (Haddow et al., 2017).

Therefore, all these activities are proactive rather than reactive in which preparedness plays a pivotal role in mitigating the financial implications of disasters. Communities have the potential to significantly reduce the costs related to disasters by directing resources toward preventive measures and preparedness strategies. This proactive approach allows communities to avoid or mitigate the damage to infrastructure and the disruption of livelihoods, which typically result in higher costs if addressed post-disaster (Lindsay, 2012).

Petley et al. (2007) interpret that awareness programs that encompass various natural and man-made disasters, such as heat waves, thunderbolts, windstorms, landslides, firefighting, monsoon response, and water-induced disasters, are crucial in the context of Nepal. Given the country's diverse and often challenging topography, these programs are essential for enhancing community resilience and preparedness. For instance, Nepal's susceptibility to landslides and earthquakes necessitates widespread education on preventive measures and emergency response protocols to minimize loss of life and property.

Moreover, Lindell and Perry (2003) state that community meetings serve as crucial mechanisms for facilitating open dialogue and the exchange of local knowledge. These forums play a pivotal role in addressing specific community needs and fostering collective problem-solving, thereby ensuring the cultural appropriateness and widespread acceptance of DM strategies. Rodríguez et al. (2007) advocate the importance of pamphlets and newspapers as the dissemination of pamphlets and posters is equally indispensable, as these resources reach a diverse audience with clear and easily accessible information that individuals can consult at their convenience.

Utilizing local media outlets like radio stations and community newspapers is vital in guaranteeing that disaster preparedness messages are conveyed even to the most isolated regions. Through these channels, timely updates and information can be broadcast during emergencies, effectively keeping the community informed and engaged. Moreover, harnessing the power of social media platforms enables the swift distribution of information and facilitates real-time communication in times of disaster. Social media platforms also have the potential to involve younger demographics, fostering a culture of readiness among individuals of all age groups (Houston et al., 2015).

Likewise, heat waves in the Terai and thunderbolts in the mountainous regions of Nepal present significant dangers, where populations are frequently cut off and lack immediate access to emergency services. Educational campaigns targeting these risks can instruct locals on self-protection measures, such as finding suitable shelter and recognizing the symptoms of hypothermia and frostbite (Shrestha & Aryal, 2011). Likewise, windstorms and water-related calamities like floods are prevalent during the monsoon season, and readiness efforts can enlighten communities about advance notification mechanisms, evacuation strategies, and secure havens, hence lessening the consequences of such occurrences (Dangal, 2011).

Likewise, Chalise et al. (2019) highlight that firefighting and monsoon response initiatives play a crucial role in urban areas, especially where there are high population densities and insufficient infrastructure, thus amplifying the impact of disasters. Equipping the public with fundamental firefighting skills and raising awareness about fire safety measures can effectively reduce the likelihood of minor incidents evolving into major crises. Furthermore, monsoon response programs are instrumental in alleviating the yearly disruptions caused by intense rainfall, by overseeing the upkeep of drainage systems and the establishment of flood shelters.

According to The National Fire Protection Association (2022), firefighting insight includes the appropriate utilization of personal protective gear, maintenance and utilization of tools and equipment, varied methods of casualty evacuation, and fundamental exercises. The preparedness of gear and staff, reaction time, collaboration with other agencies, and teamwork coordination during emergency responses help to enhance effective response during fire emergencies.

2.2.2 Capacity Building

According to Pandey and Okazaki (2005), while disasters can strike a wide region or a nation, that impact is felt at the community level however it may hit one or several communities at once. These communities constitute what is referred to as “disaster fronts”. Further, he added that to be at the forefront, communities need to have the capacity to respond to threats themselves. Therefore, communities have a very important role in managing the risks that may threaten their well-being.

Nifa et al. (2017) highlighted that capacity-building training conducted by the armed forces within communities plays a crucial role in enhancing local resilience and preparedness for disasters. These training schemes equip community members with the skills and knowledge required to effectively address emergencies and security challenges, thereby fostering self-reliance and readiness. The systematic training approaches and vast expertise of the armed forces in areas like first aid, search and rescue missions, and disaster response are of great value. This partnership not only strengthens the crisis response capabilities of the community but also cultivates trust and collaboration between the military and civilians. For example, training programs led by the military have proven to significantly enhance local response capacities, thereby reducing community susceptibility to various risks. Through investing in such capacity-building endeavours, the armed forces play a pivotal role in establishing more resilient and secure communities, consequently contributing to national stability and safety.

Therefore, because of providing essential training in first aid, search and rescue operations, and disaster response protocols, armed forces are frequently highlighted for their role in disaster preparedness training and capacity building. These trainings, awareness programs, and capacity-building activities enhance the community’s ability to respond effectively to disasters (Kapucu, 2008). Moreover, Varano and Schafer (2012) argue that Building trust and open communication between the community and security forces enhances preparedness and response efforts. Moreover, trust facilitates the sharing of vital information and ensures more effective collaboration during disasters.

Engaging in practical applications is pivotal for the proficient utilization of firefighting apparatus. Frequently, instructional courses incorporate simulated fire situations in which individuals can engage in the utilization of gas cylinders to suppress fires, ensuring their ability to effectively operate the apparatus under pressure (Secer & Satyen, 2006).

2.2.3 Community Engagement and Collaboration

When security forces and communities work together, they can leverage their respective strengths and resources to better prepare for, respond to, and recover from disasters (Shea, 2018). Community engagement and collaboration are crucial components of effective DM, and the role of security forces in this process is critical (Indrayani & Wasistiono, 2021). Security forces can serve as a bridge between the community and government agencies, facilitating communication and coordinating responses. By understanding the unique needs and challenges of local communities, security forces can tailor their approach to DM and ensure that the community is fully engaged and empowered in the process (Shaw, 2016).

Existing research highlights the importance of community participation in disaster planning and recovery efforts. Effective disaster response requires a deep understanding of community context and the enhancement of community-level capacities to work with response agencies post-disaster. Communities must be treated as equal partners, not just passive recipients of aid, to ensure the success of recovery activities (Patterson et al., 2010). Security forces can play a key role in fostering this collaborative approach by involving community members in decision-making, providing training and resources, and coordinating with other stakeholders (Paton et al., 2021).

2.2.4 Disaster Response

Armed forces possess a unique set of skills and resources that are invaluable in disaster scenarios, including rapid response capabilities, logistical support, and specialized equipment. When these capabilities are integrated into CBDM, the overall resilience and responsiveness of the community are enhanced. This integration involves coordinated planning, joint training exercises, and shared communication channels between the armed forces and local DM agencies (Rachmawati et al., 2023).

As defined by Twigg (2007), Community-based approaches to DM emphasize local ownership, with communities taking the lead in identifying risks, planning responses, and implementing recovery strategies. By integrating the armed forces into this framework, communities benefit from the added expertise and resources without losing their sense of agency and local knowledge. Joint training programs can enhance mutual understanding and cooperation, ensuring that both the military and the community are prepared to act in a coordinated manner when disasters strike (Katz, 2022).

2.2.5 Local Knowledge and Resources

According to Long and Nuckolls (1994), local knowledge and resources are essential for understanding the unique needs and characteristics of a specific community. Therefore, Communities have firsthand knowledge of their vulnerabilities, resources, and capacities. Engaging them in DM ensures that local knowledge is utilized effectively. Local resources can be mobilized quickly in times of need (Norris et al., 2008).

By integrating scientific approaches enhancing community resilience, and emphasizing the significance of integrating indigenous practices and traditional wisdom into disaster risk reduction strategies, local resources and knowledge play important roles in efficient and effective DM. Local communities often possess valuable insights, passed down through generations, on early warning signs, natural indicators, and adaptive strategies that can mitigate risks and enhance preparedness.

However, the challenge lies in preserving and transferring this knowledge to future generations, as many communities are at risk of losing these valuable resources due to a lack of documentation and formal integration into mainstream education and policy frameworks. Therefore, it is essential to prioritize the incorporation of local knowledge into DM policies, education systems, and community engagement initiatives to build more resilient and sustainable disaster response mechanisms.

2.3 APF, Nepal in Disaster Management

Initially, the establishment of APF, Nepal in 2001 was aimed at addressing the prevailing insurgency, which stunned the local police and faced legal constraints in utilizing the Nepal Army. Following the restoration of peace, the Nepal Government prioritized assigning this security force to border security, DM, and twelve other responsibilities (Armed Police Force Nepal, 2001).

Moreover, the APF plays a diverse role in border security, counter-insurgency, DM, and involvement in global peacekeeping operations. Over time, it has adapted to tackle non-traditional security dilemmas via professional growth initiatives and educational programs available at the APF Command and Staff College, associated with Tribhuvan University. The primary objective of this establishment is to enrich the expertise of mid-level officers by

furnishing them with both theoretical and practical education in security and development studies (*APF Command and Staff College, n.d.*).

APF, Nepal is actively engaged in DM as a primary responsibility. The Ministry of Home Affairs designated APF, Nepal as the key security entity for DM, leading to the establishment of the DM Training School in Kurintar, Chitwan in 2011. This institution focuses on enhancing the readiness, response, and recovery efforts through the training of skilled and confident personnel in disaster-related operations and humanitarian aid. Similarly, in furtherance of DM objectives, APF, Nepal inaugurated a Disaster Rescue Battalion in Sinamangal, Kathmandu. This battalion carries out its duties nationwide as required.

Moreover, APF, Nepal is tasked with protecting of life, property, and liberty of the people by maintaining peace and order (Aryal, 2022). During disasters or epidemics in any part of the country, APF, Nepal, has been playing a crucial role by showing the highest level of professionalism in the emergency needs of disaster victims such as search and rescue, providing shelters, and distributing relief materials (Armed Police Force, 2021).

Table 2.2

Disaster Management Unit of APF, Nepal

S.N.	Name	Remarks
1.	Disaster Management Directorate	
2.	Disaster Management Training School, Kurintar, Chitwan	
3.	High-Altitude Disaster Rescue Training School, Manang	
3.	APF, Nepal No. 20 Battalion Headquarters Disaster Rescue, Sinamangal Kathmandu	
4.	Disaster Management Base, Mulghat, Dhankuta	
5.	Disaster Management Base, Nijgadh, Bara	
6.	Disaster Management Base, Adamghat, Dhading	
7.	Disaster Management Base, Kulekhani, Makawanpur	
8.	Disaster Management Base, Khurkot, Sindhuli	
9.	Disaster Management Base, Narchyang, Magdi	
10.	Disaster Management Base, Jwalamai, Dang	
11.	Disaster Management Base, Chiple, Surkhet	

12. Disaster Management Base, Amargadhi, Dadheldhura
 13. Disaster Management Rescue Tower, Narayani Bridge, Chitwan
 14. Disaster Management Rescue Tower, Phewatal, Pokhara
-

Source: APF, Nepal Headquarters, 2024

Table 2.2 shows a detailed framework for understanding the disaster response capability of APF, Nepal. At the top, it has a DM directorate under the operational department. It has its specialized DM training school and disaster rescue battalion too. This division highlights the specialization of its structure and personnel as the training school provides the disaster-related preparedness training the battalion has been seen for the response structure.

DM in Nepal has evolved significantly over the years, with a shift towards community-based strategies that empower local populations to prepare for and respond to emergencies. The APF, Nepal of Nepal plays a pivotal role in this paradigm, integrating CBDM into its operational framework. This paper reviews the effectiveness of the CBDM initiatives, of APF, Nepal highlighting the successes and challenges faced in implementing these strategies.

In Nepal, the APF, Nepal is instrumental in CBDM by enabling local communities to serve as primary responders in times of disasters. Acknowledging the significance of communities' proximity to disaster areas and their profound understanding of the local environment, the APF prioritizes activities aimed at enhancing their capabilities (Gaillard & Gomez, 2015). Likewise, through a concentration on initiatives for building capacity, the APF, Nepal seeks to grant authority to local communities, enabling them to become more self-sufficient and adept at addressing disaster scenarios promptly. Patnaik (2023) argues that this strategy not only improves quick reaction but also nurtures a feeling of possession and proactive engagement in activities related to preparing for and reducing the impact of disasters. In contrast, Pathranarakul and Shrestha (2018) argue that the execution of CBDM tactics via the APF has encountered obstacles. Challenges like limited resources, frequent turnover in leadership, and ambiguous directives across different organizations have hindered the effectiveness of disaster response endeavours. Enhancing community involvement and ensuring sufficient training and resources for local responders are indispensable aspects requiring enhancement.

2.4 Empirical Study of Disaster Management Governance Framework

2.4.1 Global Framework

In the global framework, the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR) 2015-2030, Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), and the Paris Agreement 2015 on climate change are important documents for DM. In the context of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR) 2015-2030, security forces assume a pivotal function in CBDM. They are tasked with roles that surpass conventional law enforcement, extending to proactive initiatives aimed at decreasing disaster vulnerabilities and enhancing community resilience.

The SFDRR has focused on the local community involvement for an inclusive decision-making process including vulnerable groups, women, children, the elderly, and people with disabilities. Moreover, local Indigenous knowledge and traditional practices in disaster risk management have been kept at the centre. For CBDM this framework highlights public awareness campaigns, educational programs, and building local capacity through specific training to enhance the skills and knowledge of community members.

Likewise, this framework has recognized the role of security agencies as key stakeholders in all phases from preparedness and response to recovery and reconstruction integrating local communities to empower them for disaster risk reduction. The involvement of security agencies in information collection, dissemination promptly, and use of their resources such as communication, medical support, transport, etc. during crisis time has been emphasized.

Moreover, the Paris Agreement is a landmark global accord that has established a general framework for global climate action to address the disaster risks posed by climate change. Linking with DM, the Paris Agreement has focused on reducing greenhouse gas emissions to limit global temperature for mitigation. Likewise, enhancing adaptive capacity strengthening resilience, reducing vulnerability to the adverse impacts of climate (European Commission, 2023) change, and establishing a mechanism to adhere to loss and damage associated with climate change are the key components of the agreement.

Mobilizing finance by increasing public and private investment in disaster risk reduction and climate change, development and deployment of innovative technologies for DM, and strengthening the ability of countries and communities to prepare for and respond to disaster are the major areas of financing and support for DM.

Likewise, SDGs recognize the critical role of effective DM in achieving sustainable development. It seeks to strengthen the capacity of communities and countries to prevent, mitigate, and recover from disasters. Risk reduction and call for coordinated humanitarian assistance to support communities affected by disasters are the provisions of SDGs. It advocates to identifying and addressing vulnerabilities, investing in early warning systems, and building infrastructure that can withstand and recover from disaster.

To empower communities for disaster preparedness it emphasizes educating communities, securing the involvement of local stakeholders in disaster planning and decision-making, and capacity building through training to community members in first aid, search and rescue, and other disaster response skills to build local resilience are the key provisions of the SDGs.

2.4.2 National Framework

The Constitution of Nepal-2015, specifically in part 4 article 51, includes provisions aimed at mitigating risks associated with natural disasters. These provisions focus on implementing advanced early warning systems, and preparedness measures, as well as rescue, relief, and rehabilitation efforts within policies related to the safeguarding, advancement, and utilization of natural resources.

Similarly, schedule 7 outlines provisions for early warning systems, preparedness actions, and response measures for both natural and non-natural disasters, highlighting them as shared responsibilities among the federal, provincial, and local authorities. Furthermore, schedule 8 designates the primary responsibility for DM to be at the local level. Lastly, schedule 9 emphasizes DM as a collective responsibility of the federal, provincial, and local governments (Constitution of Nepal, 2015).

APF, Nepal was established in 2001 to mandate the maintenance of internal security, border security, and DM. So, activities were carried out during its establishment. As provisioned in the Constitution of Nepal, APF, Nepal is deploying in rescue, relief, and rehabilitation in DM under the Armed Police Act 2001. Though there are not clearly defined roles, responsibilities, and policies in the DM sector, it is deploying its personnel as provisioned in its act. Accordingly, it has been mobilizing its strength to mitigate, preparedness, rescue, distribute relief, and rehabilitate before, during, and after disaster (Armed Police Force Nepal, 2001).

Previously, there was a lack of a basic legal framework, resulting in a weak mandate. However, with the enactment of the Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act 2017, a significant change has occurred. The Ministry of Home Affairs, serving as the highest governing body, has unified the domains of 'conflict resolution' and 'DM' under a single entity known as 'the Disaster and Conflict Management Division' within the respective department (Dawadi, 2019).

Figure 2.3

Structure of Disaster Risk Reduction and Management in Nepal

Source: DRRM Act, 2017

The DRR Strategic Plan of Action 2018-2030 has been introduced in alignment with the National Risk Reduction Strategy (NRRS) 2009 as part of the Government of Nepal's commitment to implement key international agreements such as the Sendai Framework 2015-2030, Paris Agreement on Climate Change, and Sustainable Development Goals (Disaster Risk Reduction National Strategic Plan of Action, 2018).

The Sendai Framework is considered a guiding principle at the international level, while the NRRS serves as the guiding framework for DRRM at the national level. Furthermore, the Government of Nepal has enacted the DRRM Act 2017 to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of DM, outlining the establishment and functions of the Local Disaster Management Committee (LDMC) and its responsibilities in mobilizing various stakeholders, including the local community. Local government is tasked with the primary responsibility of CBDM as stipulated by the Act. Additionally, there is a provision for establishing rescue and preparedness committees at the Ward and community levels to facilitate immediate response

and mobilization during disasters (*Local Government Operation Act, 2018*). Furthermore, security forces are entrusted with conducting programs aimed at promoting disaster response preparedness and relief awareness among educational institutions, local communities, and informal social collectives.

The legislation known as the LGO Act of 2018 in Nepal includes clauses related to CBDM to empower local governments in the realm of disaster preparedness and response. A key requirement of this legislation is the establishment of Disaster Management Committees by local governments at both the municipality and rural municipality levels. These committees have been assigned the responsibility of creating DM strategies, carrying out assessments of risks, and implementing actions for risk reduction in cooperation with pertinent stakeholders, which may include members of the community. Moreover, the legislation grants local governments the necessary resources and authority to deploy staff and assets for efficient DM within their respective areas. These provisions are designed to strengthen community resilience and diminish disaster risks at the grassroots level.

2.5 Research Gap

APF, Nepal is deploying in all DM phases: pre-disaster, during disaster, and post-disaster. It is performing well by conducting special training for its personnel and has seen the output very efficient and effective in the rescue operation.

Though the Constitution of Nepal and subsequent legislation outline the deployment of APF, Nepal in DM activities, there is a lack of specific roles and responsibilities. It is deploying and rescuing the persons and property affected by the disaster but lacks clarity and definition of roles and responsibilities. Likewise, there is a lack of insight and the review doesn't provide sufficient knowledge into how APF, Nepal's initiatives are integrating with local community activities.

It is very essential to understand the extent to which the APF, Nepal collaborates and coordinates with local authorities and community-based organization. Moreover, the review shows the APF, Nepal is conducting various initiatives aimed at promoting disaster response preparedness and relief awareness to empower local communities, educational institutions, and informal groups of society, but there is little research or literature on organizational involvement in the academic field.

Addressing these research gaps could enhance comprehension regarding the involvement of the APF, Nepal in CBDM and provide insights for refining policies and practices to enhance the efficiency of disaster risk reduction activities.

CHAPTER III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this chapter is to provide a detailed examination of the methodological choices that were taken to answer the research question. This includes the description of the research design adopted during the study. Moreover, it describes the targeted population and sample selection with the use of sampling techniques. Data collection and analysis techniques along with its models are also well narrated in this chapter.

3.1 Research Design

The study employs a descriptive research design. Moreover, qualitative research methods are used to describe and analyze the available data. Key Informant Interviews (KII), with semi-structured questionnaires, were employed to analyze activities, experience, and understanding of the engagement of APF, Nepal personnel in CBDM. Interviews enable researchers to pose additional inquiries. The secondary data are also presented and explained qualitatively.

According to Merriam and Tisdell (2015), employing the qualitative view helps to construct their reality in interactions with their social worlds. In basic qualitative research, the data is often collected through interviews, which allow for in-depth exploration of topics. Likewise, qualitative data employs, normally, a smaller sample size and doesn't necessarily represent a large number of populations as quantitative data may do. Furthermore, explains that qualitative research "focuses on describing, understanding, and clarifying a human experience and therefore qualitative studies are directed at describing the aspects that make up an idiosyncratic experience rather than determining the most likely, or mean experience, within a group." (Dornyei, 2007). Therefore, this study has employed 5 KII for an in-depth understanding of the subject matter.

The primary objective of qualitative research is active involvement in the study. Likewise, according to Dornyei (2007), interviews are predominantly utilized in applied linguistics. Melles (2005), further asserts that qualitative interviewing focuses on acquiring genuine data regarding the respondent's subjective perspective by establishing rapport and empathy through researcher sensitivity. Through face-to-face interviews with participants, researchers could ensure alignment between responses and questions. Demonstrating comprehension and nodding were also strategies to cultivate trust.

Therefore, this study has employed a descriptive research design with qualitative data analysis utilizing KII, and the Secondary database for a deeper understanding of the phenomena.

3.2 Methodological Framework

Figure 3.1

Methodological Framework of the Study

3.3 Nature and Sources of Data

All the collected data are of a qualitative nature and have been collected from both primary and secondary sources.

3.3.1 Primary Sources

For an informative understanding of a particular subject matter, a non-probability judgemental sampling technique has been employed in this study. According to (Etikan, 2016), judgmental sampling allows researchers to focus on specific subgroups that are particularly informative. The sample represents a fragmented population of the targeted population (Collis & Hussey, 2014). Thus, for the study, the primary information was collected from KII administering in-depth open-ended questioner for a deep understanding of the subject matter. KII was conducted among five informants: 3 informants from APF, Nepal Disaster Management Training School (DMTS), 1 informant from a local representative of Ichhyakamana Village Municipality, and 1 informant from Kathmandu Metropolitan City Juddha Baraunyantra, on the judgmental sampling method.

3.3.2 Secondary Sources

Legal provisions of DM and CBDM, moreover, various awareness and capacity building programs carried out by APF, and Nepal-related literature were collected as secondary data for the research study. Published journals, articles, books, reports, and archives have been gathered from the website and online sources.

3.4 Techniques of Data Analysis

This research has adopted thematic analysis transcribing KII and secondary data recovered from APF, Nepal. Thematic analysis, a qualitative data analysis method widely employed gained significance since the late 1990s (Kiger & Varpio, 2020). Described as accessible, flexible, and progressively favored, it provides a methodical approach to qualitative data analysis (Luciani et al., 2019). Moreover, thematic analysis, a commonly employed analytical technique in qualitative research, offers a structured and adaptable strategy for discerning, examining, and presenting patterns or themes present in data (Mishra & Dey, 2022). Therefore, this research has adopted thematic analysis transcribing KII. For thematic analysis, the following steps were followed.

3.4.1 Transcriptions

All collected information from the KII were properly drafted in a note. The transcriptions of the KII provided well-structured written documents to process further.

3.4.2 Coding

After the transcriptions, all written documents were thoroughly analysed and coded based on the most repeated words, phrases, and concepts. The coding in the study supports understanding the main key themes for the discussion.

3.4.3 Thematic Categorization

The identified key themes were reviewed deeply to generate the findings and were discussed accordingly in the study. The thematic categorization in this study supported an understanding of how APF, Nepal is contributing to CBDM through its different initiatives.

3.5 Ethical Consideration

The ethical aspect is crucial in research efforts, serving as a fundamental element in preserving the study's integrity and ensuring the rights and well-being of the participants. Obtaining informed consent is fundamental, requiring researchers to fully inform participants about the nature of the research, including its purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits, and to obtain their voluntary agreement to participate (Creswell, 2009). Maintaining confidentiality and anonymity is crucial to protect participants' identities and personal information (Patton, 2014). This study has furnished all the necessary ethical considerations by maintaining confidentiality.

CHAPTER IV

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The chapter in the study has discussed the secondary data collected for the study and the responses of KII by generating key themes from the thematic analysis. Based on the presented themes, the chapter also discussed key issues identified by the study.

4.1 Awareness Program: Linkage of Community and APF, Nepal

According to Bali (2022), disaster awareness initiatives are very important in establishing connections between communities and security forces through the enhancement of preparedness, response, and resilience. These programs, as highlighted in various research papers, emphasize the importance of community involvement in disaster risk reduction activities. Moreover, implementing disaster preparedness education programs, like those conducted in schools and communities, can significantly enhance the disaster awareness and preparedness of young children, and community groups by contributing to overall community resilience (Herdiansyah et al., 2020).

As NDRRMA provisioned roles and responsibilities of various agencies, the secondary data reviewed in the study shows that APF, Nepal has been conducting awareness programs among school children and community groups. The 4.1 table highlights the total awareness training conducted by APF, Nepal from 2080/01/01 to 2081/12/30.

Table 4.1

Awareness Program Conducted by APF, Nepal

S.N	Events/Exercise	NO. Ex	Schools		Community		Total
			Male	Female	Male	Female	
1.	Heat wave	96					
	Landslide	188					
	Windstorm	71					
	Firefighting	281	17081	18016	24540	25231	84868
	Monsoon	195					
	Response						

Water induced disaster	91
Disaster management	277
Thunderbolt	61

Source: APF, Nepal Headquarters, 2024

Table 4.1 shows that APF, Nepal has conducted various awareness programs in schools and communities from which 85,868 persons have been educated in the different disaster-related fields. It shows the proactive effort to minimize the risk and response during the disaster. Similarly, further shows that awareness programs that include cold waves, thunderbolts, windstorms, landslides, firefighting, monsoon response, water-induced disaster, and, disaster management are key to empowering the community. During the awareness program, 35,097 (17081 Male, and 18016 Female) school children and 49,771 (24,540 Male and 25,231 Female) community members participated. It shows the high level of participation of the people in disaster preparedness.

The reviewed data showed that the wide participation in various awareness programs in schools and communities adheres proactive effort of APF, Nepal to minimize the risk and response during disaster. Similarly, awareness programs that include heat waves, thunderbolts, windstorms, landslides, firefighting, monsoon response, water-induced disaster, and, DM have been focused on during the session. These programs are very essential and actively needed as stated by Petley et al. (2007) considering the nation’s diverse and often challenging topography. Moreover, focusing on heat waves and thunderbolt hazards helps in seeking appropriate shelter and understanding the signs of hypothermia hyperthermia, and frostbite as highlighted by (Dangal, 2011). Likewise, training in basic firefighting techniques and promoting fire safety awareness, and monsoon response programs can help mitigate the disruption caused by rains (Chalise et al., 2019).

The study shows that APF, Nepal has been working closely with local government and community to promote the community of practice for DM. During the study, one of the participants from APF, Nepal DMTS, Kurintar, shared his experience,

“I have been working in CBDM for 9 years and have conducted 300 awareness programs. In this journey, what I have realized is that CBDM is one of the effective tools to engage with the

local community that not only contributes to CBDM initiatives but also connects APF with locals”

Similarly, A junior commissioned officer who has 13 years of experience as a practitioner in the CBDM field with more than 700 awareness and capacity-building programs also shared that,

“CBDM is not just a program, it is an approach where all stakeholders within a community come together to initiate the solution to mitigate and manage the disaster”

During the KII with one of the senior officers of APF, Nepal shared that there are normally no schedules and guidelines to conduct such CBDM programs whether monthly or annually, but it is according to need and cooperation with the local community. He further added,

“Based on the need identification we conduct various awareness programs on DM: firefighting, earthquake, landslides, disaster risk mitigation, road accidents, first aid, etc. to the community, local government body, agencies, and informal groups. Sometimes we collaborate with local media, and newspapers and disseminate information using social media.”

While having a KII from Kathmandu Metro Juddha Barun Yantra the officials shared his experience of firefighting awareness programs:

“I have learned many basic things about modern advanced tools to use especially in firefighting which has given insight into effective application during disaster. The proper use of personal protective equipment, maintenance, and use of tools and equipment, different techniques of casualty evacuation, and basic drills to be followed were the crucial part of training. The readiness of equipment and personnel, response timing, coordination with other agencies, and coordination among the team while responding to the emergencies were fruitful.”

He also acknowledges the contribution of security forces for their assistance during the time of emergency by highlighting the skills of security forces.

“During the time of response, security agencies play an import role not only in managing the mass but their response skills assist us in multiple ways”

The study found that the perception of community people towards APF and their contribution to CBDM was very useful and respectful. KII from Ichhyakamana Village Municipality stated that:

“The presence of APF, in Nepal has played a very important role in educating the community to rescue operations occur through the Prithivi Highway. The classes on road accidents and first aid have made it easy to respond community as first responders and save the lives of the people by giving basic medical treatment. Normally, what should we do during a disaster, how to communicate with concerned authority, techniques to evacuate during earthquake and fire, and things to consider while acting during emergencies were key areas of learning.”

The study found that disaster awareness in emergency response techniques, first aid, fire safety, and earthquake safety which has been focused on by Haddow et al. (2017) in their research as CBDM activities provide the necessary expertise and understanding to effectively react in emergencies.

The significance of emergency response methods, initial medical assistance, fire prevention, earthquake preparedness, and flood prevention initiatives are paramount in this context. Moreover, emphasizing CBDM by APF, Nepal supports Lindsay (2012), the effectiveness of preparedness helps to mitigate the financial implications of disaster and this proactive approach plays a crucial role in avoiding and mitigating disruption of livelihoods, and damage to infrastructure which costs high if not addressed timely.

The radio and local community newspapers are crucial to reach to even remote areas that broadcast timely information and updates during emergencies (Rodríguez et al., 2007). Moreover, Houston et al. (2015) also support awareness activities through social media allows for rapid dissemination of information and real-time communication.

During the KII, it was identified that APF, Nepal has been distributing pamphlets, educating school children and the community through workshops and training, community meetings, and using social media and local media (Radio, TV, etc.) as a tool to reach out to the community in disseminating the awareness message regarding the DM.

Moreover, Shiwaku and Shaw (2008) stated that these kinds of awareness programs not only safeguard life but also minimize the disruption to education caused by disaster. APF, Nepal's initiative to CBDM has shown extensive engagement in awareness programs to make the

community people prepared for the unforeseen disaster. These activities mark a significant contribution to building resilience and preparedness among local communities and school children.

4.2 Capacity Building and Simulation Activities Strengthening CBDM

Kapucu (2008) argues that the trainings and capacity-building activities enhance the community's ability to respond effectively to disasters. Similarly, Varano and Schafer (2012) also focused on building trust and open communication between the community and security forces to enhance preparedness and response efforts. Moreover, trust facilitates the sharing of vital information and ensures more effective collaboration during disasters.

KI from APF, Nepal shared his experience that, local people were found very cooperative and willing to get involved in such programs. He stated that:

“In many communities, at first when we ask the question how do you think to extinguish the fire when cooking-gas caught fire? The answer was, using water. Some of them were used to being afraid too much of such type of fire. When we instructed them that there is always a gap of fire between the Nossal of the gas pipe and the fire which can be prevented just by putting our finger to the hole with precaution, they became so amazed. Likewise, we also learned about how to cover the fire with a blanket, especially when wet. Moreover, the types of fire, types of extinguisher cylinder, operating procedure of gas cylinder, and the precaution of, safety and response methods were taught and exercised in the session.”

During the KII one senior officer stated:

most of the responses about the local community were found prepared for any type of disaster after getting capacity building training whereas unprepared responses found less. In Ichhyakamana Village Municipality we can see the fire extinguishers, emergency exit doors, and assembling points during a disaster are well set and allocated.

Nifa et al. (2017) state that the collaboration with local community not only strengthens response capability but also fosters trust and cooperation between civil and military. Likewise, KI from Kathmandu Municipality Juddha Barunyantra highlighted the crucial aspect of coordination among different agencies during a disaster. Similarly, he explained the importance of the capacity building through simulation exercises on firefighting which helped

to enhance the practical knowledge about personal safety, skills, and readiness of participants. According to him:

“Practical knowledge educated us to handle firefighting equipment, size up the scene and safely rescue the victims by search and rescue operations. Moreover, the practical training has built confidence ensuring act swiftly and effectively during emergencies. Moreover, it has taught the importance of teamwork, and communication as rescuers must coordinate important information under pressure. The simulation was very crucial to enhance community safety and resilience, preparing the responder to protect lives and property when real fires occur.”

Similarly, KI from Ichhyakamana Village Municipality shared his experience of capacity-building training on earthquake and road accidents. He stated that:

“These trainings remain fruitful which have given insight on securing the scene by quick and safe response techniques. It also enhanced knowledge of providing basic medical care, and coordination with other emergency services and concerned authorities to reduce the severity and save lives. Understanding seismic risks, structural safety measures, and personal safety action during earthquake emergencies were very fruitful. These kinds of training contribute to building stronger, and more informed communities capable of mitigating the effect and impact of road accidents and earthquakes, which ultimately helps to reduce casualties, property damage, and societal disruption.”

The secondary data reviewed in the study showed that APF Nepal is contributing to CBDM by implementing different initiatives as discussed below.

Table 4.2

Capacity-Building Trainings

S. N.	Events/Exercise	NO. Ex	Schools		Community		Total
			Male	Female	Male	Female	
1.	Air-crash and mass casualty evacuation	97	4,087	2,617	20,160	20,609	47,473
	Firefighting	217					

Earthquake	298
Collapsed Structure Search and Rescue (CSSR)	45
First Aid	266

Source: APF, Nepal Headquarters. It shows the number of awareness programs conducted by APF, Nepal from 2080/01/01 to 2081/12/30

Table 4.2 shows that APF, Nepal has conducted various capacity-building and simulation programs in schools and communities from which 47,473 have been educated in the different disaster-related fields. The exercises were mass casualty evacuation, firefighting, earthquake, collapsed structure search and rescue, and first aid by conducting 923 exercises, which shows these CBDM activities have covered a wide range of participants in the disaster field. Mostly, earthquake exercise can be seen highest number of sessions with 298. It may be because of its high vulnerability of Nepal in earthquake disasters and the losses it faced in the 2015 earthquake. The high level of priority on seismic risk exercise shows that more priority has been given by APF, Nepal. Moreover, first aid with 266 has seen a substantial number of sessions. CSSR and mass casualty evacuation 45 and 97 events respectively have been seen less in numbers. The study shows that though there is a disparity in school-based participation by gender, community participation has been well-balanced. In support, Byrne and Callaghan (2013) emphasize that there is still room for improvement to make them fully participate by addressing the barriers.

Overall, mostly the focus has been seen on high-risk scenarios in the context of Nepal like earthquakes, firefighting, and first aid. It highlights the crucial effort in the capacity-building field in terms of CBDM by emphasizing the importance of preparedness, enabling communities to practice response plans, and enhancing the effectiveness of disaster response strategies as stated by (World Health Organization, 2023).

4.3 Resources and Capability of APF, Nepal to Enhance CBDM

The secondary information reviewed for the study shows that APF, Nepal poses a strong capability in CBDM as the organization has 2669 trained individuals highly capable of advanced response skills such as Collapsed Structure Search and Rescue (CSSR), Swift Water Search and Rescue (SWSS), Deep Diving and so on as shown in table 4.3.

Table 4.3*Training and Trained Manpower of APF, Nepal in DM*

S.N.	Training	Trained Manpower
1.	CSSR	
2.	SWSS	
3.	Deep Diving	
4.	Fire Fighting	2669
5.	Dead Body Management (DBM)	
6.	MFR	
7.	Rope Rescue	
8.	Cable Car Rescue (CCR)	
	Total	2669

Source: APF, Nepal Headquarters, 2024

Similarly, deep diving is related to the underwater search and rescue operation in which trapped and drowning persons are rescued from rivers, ponds, or lakes. APF, Nepal has trained and prepared its manpower to handle fire outbreaks whether in urban or rural. Therefore, table 4.3 shows this security agency is prepared and preparing its personnel to fight and handle fire effectively.

Moreover, preparing for DBM helps to prepare personnel for handling respectfully, and safely manage the deceased body during disaster. So, this table shows the APF, Nepal is fully prepared in the DBM scenario, too. Similarly, it is shown that this organization is conducting medical first aid training for the immediate field medical service and to provide initial medical care in emergencies. Likewise, rope rescue and cable car rescue training are also included as per Table 4.3 which plays a crucial role in rescuing from difficult terrain such as cliffs, rocks, and mountains. The focus on cable car rescue training prepares personnel to rescue and address the potential emergency risk.

As Righi et al. (2021) stated comprehensive training in disaster management is crucial due to the increasing human and economic losses caused by disasters, the study found that APF, Nepal is conducting various skillful comprehensive training in the DM sector indicates a holistic and strategic approach in disaster preparedness. Moreover, Challenges in responding to disasters stem from a lack of knowledge and skills, leading to inefficiencies and chaos during

emergencies (Exadaktylos, 2021). By ensuring a significant number of training and trained personnel, APF, Nepal is well prepared to address multiple potential disaster emergencies, and threats in diverse geography like Nepal.

4.3.1 First Aid

According to Ben-noun (2023), first aid involves providing immediate care to individuals suffering from minor or severe illnesses or injuries to maintain life, prevent deterioration, or facilitate recovery. This may entail administering crucial assistance in critical situations before professional medical assistance is accessible, like performing CPR while awaiting an ambulance, along with addressing minor ailments like applying bandages to wounds.

Medical First Responders (MFR) are essential in disaster management as they offer prompt medical assistance and aid to individuals impacted by disasters. The rapid response of these professionals is vital in stabilizing patients, delivering life-saving treatments, and averting additional harm or complexities. As the initial responders on the scene, medical first responders play a crucial role in promptly assessing and prioritizing patients to ensure those with the most severe injuries receive the necessary critical care (Marvel & Budhram, 2015). Additionally, Moreover, they are equipped with the necessary skills to operate effectively in challenging circumstances, collaborating with various emergency response entities to oversee the chaotic environment encountered in situations of disaster (Killian et al., 2017).

The secondary data reviewed in the study found that APF, Nepal is conducting first-aid training to prepare its personnel as first responders during disasters. This knowledge helps to give basic treatment. Stabilize the condition of patients, and transport them to the hospital.

Table 4.4

First-Aid Training Manual of DMTS, Kurintar

S.N.	Subject	Methods	
		L	Ex
1.	First-aid and medical emergencies: Introduction, types, reason, signs and symptoms and methods	2	1
2.	Lifting and moving patient: Introduction, types, methods of carrying patients	2	4
3.	Triage: Introduction and methods	2	2
4.	Incident reporting and report writing	2	-
5.	First-aid treatment to water-drowned	2	1

6.	Patient assessment: Introduction, preliminary information, general principle of physical check-up	1	2
7.	Bone fracture: Introduction, first-aid methods and basic consideration	2	1
8.	Basic Life Support and Cardio Pulmonary Resuscitation (CPR): Introduction, first-aid methods and basic consideration	-	4
9.	Oxygen therapy: Introduction, methods of using and basic consideration; Hemorrhage and shock: Introduction, types and symptoms, and methods of treatment	4	3
10.	Soft tissue injuries and treatment methods	-	4
11.	Introduction, types, symptoms/signs, and first-aid for injuries to muscles and skeletal system	4	
12.	Introduction, types, symptoms/signs, and first-aid for injuries to the head, spine, and chest		
13.	Environmental emergencies and burns: Introduction, types, causes, symptoms/signs, and first-aid procedures		
14.	Poisoning: Introduction, ways poison enters the body, symptoms/signs, and first-aid procedures		
15.	Rescue techniques in vehicle accidents, safety precautions, and information on the use of rescue equipment	2	2
16.	Introduction to airplane accidents and safety measures to be adopted during rescue operations	1	-
17.	MFR: Introduction, objectives, qualities, roles and responsibilities	2	-
18.	Infectious diseases and protection: Introduction, modes of disease transmission, symptoms of diseases, types, and methods of prevention	2	-
19.	The incident: Introduction, types, information collecting at the accident scene, safety at the incident site, selection of entry points		2

Source: APF, Nepal Disaster Management Training School, 2024. Here, L= lecture and Ex = exercise.

Table 4.4 shows that APF, Nepal is conducting first-aid training including various subjects such as incident reporting, first-aid, checking the responsiveness of the patients, and methods of carrying them to the vehicles. Moreover, identifying the use of poison, accidents, high altitude sickness treatment, infectious diseases, basic treatment of burns, etc are also included. Basic first-aid to water-induced disaster patients, and airplane crash rescue and first-aid treatment to them have been seen well included.

KII from APF, Nepal non-commissioned officer shared his experience in conducting training:

“These basic first-aid subjects have played a crucial role in saving the lives of people mainly in accidents through the Prithivi Highway. As we have a Trauma hospital inside our DMTS office the basic treatment of the patients in the field and transporting them as the fast means of

transportation have saved the lives of many people. Normally, trainees are taught to apply basic first-aid and ensure the stable condition of patients.”

Community-centric training programs that concentrate on prehospital trauma care and strategies for disaster readiness are notably effective in enhancing bystanders' promptness in responding to emergencies (Fatoni et al., 2022). During the KII with local representative of Ichhyakamana Village Municipality shared the importance of MFR training to save life of people during disasters and even normal accidents. Further, he stated that:

“Prithivi High Way is the most accident-prone area due to narrow road construction and just side of Trishuli river. Most of the vehicles fall into the river and sometimes have to be rescued from slopy areas. Moreover, the offices of the security forces are not all the way. Therefore, if an accident happens the locals have to respond first. The Medical First Responder training has developed skills on the basic treatment of wounds, methods of controlling bleeding, clearing the airways, and checking the severeness of the patients.”

This training has emphasized comprehensive rescue methods of rescue operations which not only include the rescue task but also the basic on-site treatment to stabilize the condition of the patients. As Boev et al. (2022) stated first aid training is essential in the context of accident and disaster response as it imparts individuals with the vital knowledge and skills needed to deliver immediate assistance, potentially resulting in the preservation of lives and a decrease in morbidity. Similarly, various training approaches, including lectures, demonstrations, and role-playing, have proven to significantly enhance participants' proficiency in fundamental life-saving techniques, wound management, and evacuation protocols, enabling them to serve as initial responders in crisis (Qona’ah et al., 2023).

4.3.2 Search and Rescue Operations

According to Bortolin (2024), during disaster situations, search and rescue operations are of paramount importance in the identification and locating of individuals who are trapped or injured. Urban search and rescue teams are expert units equipped with specialized training to navigate through dangerous environments and administer medical treatment to entangled individuals, underscoring the significance of adequate training and evaluation of the scene.

The secondary data reviewed in the study found that APF, Nepal has been conducting various search and rescue techniques during disaster management. The following table 4.4 shows the different training:

Table 4.5

Collapsed Structured Search and Rescue Training Manuals

S. N.	Subject	Methods	
		L	Ex
1.	Structural triage and International Search and Rescue Advisory Group (INSARAG) building marking system	6	2
2.	Soaring method	2	6
3.	Rescue strategies and technique	4	8
4.	Construction materials, structure and damage type	2	1
5.	Search Location Techniques	2	2
6.	Lifting and Stabilizing loads	2	

Source: APF, Nepal Disaster Management Training School, 2024. In the above table L= lecture and Ex = exercise.

The study also shows that the professionally skilled APF Personnel are sharing their knowledge and skills through different activities and initiatives among community members. One KII respondent a non-commissioned officer from APF Nepal shared that:

“In our training manual, we have included a clear outline to follow the protocols and apply different skills during the response to any disaster or crisis. CSSR typically enhances the skill of rescue from collapsed structures, which is very effective in disasters such as earthquakes, landslides, etc. which has been proved by APF, Nepal in the 2015 Barpak earthquake where thousands of people were rescued from the debris.”

Likewise, another KII senior officer shared his experience about rescuing the Trishuli bus accidents:

“Firstly, we should wear full PPEs properly for self-safety, and making hitches, use of pulley to uplift the vehicle, and soaring the vehicle to make holes were the practical and important parts of the training. This training specially taught participants that with safety measures, wearing full personal protective equipment how to make hitches and use of pulley to uplift the vehicle from the downward slope, how to operate water search and rescue tasks by using rubber boats,

and provide basic first aid treatments to victims. Moreover, comprehensive knowledge on almost all kinds of disasters that happen in Nepal has made the situation work effectively.”

The study finds that APF, Nepal has been engaging in CSSR training for effective and efficient operation during disasters. These training skills enhance the community rescue and response activity, too as Bodas et al. (2019) found training programs, like search and rescue skills for trainees, have been shown to significantly improve resilience, self-efficacy, and knowledge retention post-training, aiding in better coping with major earthquakes.

4.3.3 Firefighting

According to Gold (2022), firefighting involves various aspects, from training improvements to innovative equipment. Research on Military Firemen highlighted the effectiveness of intensive training programs in enhancing air consumption during firefighting efforts. Firefighting training is essential for mitigating the consequences of fires and preserving human life. Research emphasizes the importance of fire safety instruction in enhancing individuals' understanding and response to fire occurrences (Nyankuru et al., 2017). Moreover, research findings suggest that fire safety education enhances individuals' awareness of fire safety measures and enhances their response to fire emergencies, ultimately reducing fire-related harm and fatalities (Huseyin & Satyen, 2006).

The secondary data reviewed in the study identified that APF, Nepal conducts firefighting training by focusing on basic fire to the nature of fire and extinguishing methods. The following table 4.6 shows the firefighting techniques and methods of using equipment to extinguish the fire and minimize the potential risk.

Table 4.6

Firefighting Training Manual of DMTS, Kurintar

S.N	Subject	Methods	
		L	Ex
1.	Introduction of fire, terminologies, and Personal Protective Equipments (PPE)	2	1
2.	Classification and chemistry of fire, causes of fire and principles of extinction	2	4
3.	Fire extinguishing methods, types of equipment and use of fire extinguisher	2	2
4.	Fire engines, sprinkler system, drenchers, risers, hose-reel, hydrants	2	-

5.	Salvage: Rescue of casualties and resuscitation	2	1
6.	Introduction of ladders, use and resuscitation	1	2
7.	Breathing apparatus: equipment usage and handling	2	1

Source: APF, Nepal Disaster Management Training School, 2024. Here, L= lecture and Ex = exercise.

The study found that understanding the fire concept, fire behaviour techniques, and tools for suppression have been included in the training manual. Moreover, practical knowledge of using firefighting which helps to understand the functionality and importance of each component has been seen well embedded in training. Table 4.6 showed the lecture and exercise on the practical proper use of breathing apparatus gives a more comprehensive understanding as well as practical knowledge.

One KII senior officer from APF, Nepal shared his experience about real-world firefighting scenarios. He stated that:

“The practical drills were extremely effective in preparing for real-world scenarios. The simulation exercises a real fire situation, allowing us to apply what we learned by ensuring the PPE, safety measures, and coordinating with friends for fire suppression was practically valuable.”

Likewise, the KII from Juddhabarun Yantra, Kathmandu who had participated in firefighting training also stated that:

“The lecturer and practical knowledge of firefighting is very useful in our daily as well as professional life. It has influenced my understanding by learning the importance of quick and decisive action to reduce the risk of fire. Moreover, the practical knowledge has made me more confident and efficient in responding the fire disasters.”

Furthermore, as he learned many techniques and methods of fire suppression and gained confidence, he recommends that other agencies take part in such exercises.

“As it encompasses the comprehensive curriculum, with a practical exercise, it helps to equip necessary skills and knowledge on handling various fire scenarios other agencies also have to be involved in such type of exercise. Disaster may happen in any area and any time so there

may not be availability of certain trained personnel and it can be suppressed by the collective action of all it is necessary to all agency.”

One KII from Ichhkamana Village Municipality communicated his experience of participation in a firefighting exercise:

“One-week firefighting simulation exercise extremely provided us the practical knowledge to quickly and effectively respond to fire incidents before they escalate and cause more damage to property, and human life. To become calm and be equipped with the firefighting equipment before attacking the fire ensures safety which was lacking with us as a local community member.”

The study shows the APF, Nepal conducts firefighting training and simulation with other agencies and the local community to enhance CBDM activities. It shows that the Juddhabarun Yantra firefighters and the locals of Ichhyakamana Village Municipality have profited from the practical knowledge of fire suppression and safety measures. Therefore, the importance of such training to the local community as Bali (2022) stated, plays an important role in community-based disaster management by enhancing the capacity of individuals and organizations to respond effectively during disasters. Community involvement in disaster risk reduction activities has been proven to reduce losses during disaster events, showing the significance of training and skill development for communities

4.3.4 Casualty Evacuation Procedures

Evacuation procedures within the realm of disaster management play a pivotal role in reducing casualties and safeguarding the welfare of the community in the event of natural disasters or unforeseen crises. The effectiveness of evacuation preparation encompasses the examination of governance components, encompassing policies and tactics, along with technical elements including infrastructure and communication systems (Akma et al., 2023).

During the study, it was found that the APF, Nepal conducts training for its personnel for effective evacuation from vehicles during road accidents and from debris in earthquakes and landslides. One non-commissioned officer shared his experience of earthquake rescue in 2015. He stated that:

“I have experience of rescuing Pemba Lama in the 2015 earthquake in Kathmandu using drill machine and rotatory saw to cut the slab. And finally, he was rescued live after 120 hours from the debris. The evacuation team was well-trained. So, they stabilized the victim with basic medical measures, checked all the health conditions, and evacuated by making a hole with the help of rotatory rescue. Because of well-trained manpower, we successfully shifted him to hospital.”

Likewise, one KII Senior Officer of APF, Nepal explained his experience of rescuing a victim from the bus accident. He said that:

“A person’s leg was trapped by iron rod for a long time when a bus accident occurred at Mugling, Chitwan. The complication was that the leg was trapped under the rod of the vehicle for 5 hours. The basic thing is that when we pull him out directly it will cause a life threatening to the victim. Because the trapped leg can’t circulate blood with the other parts of the body, which may cause poison. So, if we drag him out removing the rod, blood could circulate to another part of the body and heart as well, that may cause serious injuries even death. So, we bandaged the leg properly consulting with the doctors by communicating by phone, and transported him in our Bus-ambulance to Trauma Centre Kurintar.”

As the study shows there is the crucial role of coordination with other agencies during the evacuation. Furthermore, he added that:

“Normally, APF, Nepal is conduction training collaboration with other agencies which helps to work efficiently during emergencies. The role of local police to make authentic documentation and the presence of local representatives is mandatory as the legal provision ensured in the LGO Act and other documents. The disaster itself is devastating and there is need for all agencies and local people to have effective and efficient rescue operations. It also gives a chance to know the capability of the agencies and coordinate during a disaster.”

Casualty evacuation is very important within the realm of disaster management as it facilitates the prompt and secure transportation of individuals in need to suitable healthcare establishments, consequently reducing both the loss of human lives and the extent of suffering. Similarly, the study shows that the skillful CSSR and MFR team plays a vital role in saving the life of people who conducts their operations focusing on the safety of the victims.

4.4 Collaborative Exercise with Other Agency to Enhance CBDM

Sorensen et al. (2019) state that collaborative exercises are of paramount importance in the field of disaster management as they contribute significantly to the enhancement of preparedness, team cohesion, and learning outcomes. Studies have shown that exercises involving collaboration across different sectors have the potential to enhance preparedness and team integration efforts. Furthermore, these exercises play a crucial role in the enhancement of competencies associated with disaster management and readiness for emergencies, particularly in situations characterized by infrequent occurrences of mass casualty incidents, as exemplified by the COVID-19 pandemic which prompted the creation of effective virtual simulations (Kayano et al., 2023).

The secondary data reviewed in the study shows that APF Nepal has been collaborating with different agencies and organizations which is enhancing CBDM activities. The table 4.7 Shows the collaborative exercise conducted by APF, Nepal.

Table 4.7

Details of collaboration with different agencies and APF Nepal for CBDM

S. N.	Agency	Program	Participants
1.	Gorkha Welfare Trust	Basic disaster preparedness and response	26
2.	Kathmandu Municipality	Fire control: Precaution and rescue and road accident	27
3.	National Administrative College	Basic disaster preparedness and response	80
4.	Special Task Force Trainees, Nepal Police	Rafting and river crossing techniques module	115
5.	Lions Club Kathmandu	CBDM	15
6.	Coordinating with US Embassy to APF team	MFR	19
7.	National Administrative College, Jawalakhel	Basic disaster preparedness and response	79

8.	National Administrative College	Basic disaster preparedness and response	92
		Total	453

Source: APF, Nepal Disaster Management Training School, 2024

Table 4.7 shows that the different agencies received disaster-related training from APF, Nepal. It has been conducting various trainings in the CBDM in collaboration with other agencies to enhance local disaster preparedness and response capabilities.

Study shows that the basic disaster preparedness and response training with Gorkha Welfare Trust and National Administrative College emphasizes the importance of grassroots-level training. Likewise, fire control, precaution, rescue, and road accidents have provided essential skills and knowledge on the subject matter for a more resilient community.

As enhancing CBDM is the crucial subject matter of APF, Nepal, it is found by the study that civic organizations like Lions Clubs are also involved in promoting disaster preparedness at the community level. Similarly, for more advanced skills in MFR the APF, Nepal is collaborating with US Embassy, too. Moreover, as the Nepal Police is also a key actor of CBDM, there can be seen wide participation in water-swift disaster response training.

One KII from Juddhabarun Yantra, Kathmandu shared his insight about the importance of collaborative training:

“The joint DM trainings focusing on various stakeholders, including the locals and government agencies are more beneficial to enhance community preparedness and response. We can build stronger and more resilient community by sharing knowledge and resources which helps to create a sense of community ownership and responsibility.”

The study found that these trainings have built the closer relationships among the participating agencies that enhance the cooperation during the disaster. Further, he stated that:

“Conducting such collaborative training builds good and closer relationships among the organization which makes it easy to work together in a disaster. Moreover, it has made us understand each other’s protocols and capabilities which helps to lead to more effective and efficient disaster response. Moreover, this collaborative training environment can identify and address the potential communication gaps and operational challenges of each other, too.”

Similarly, KII a senior officer from APF, Nepal highlighted the fruitfulness of collaborative training. He stated that:

“As it highlights the collective knowledge and resources of the different agencies by working together participants can share their best practices and develop a fine strategy that addresses the disaster risks. Such programs also create the environment for strong network and trust which are crucial during disaster rescue.”

The collaboration with different agencies to conduct CBDM initiatives highlights that the NDRRM framework focused on disaster preparedness and response. Likewise, as APF, Nepal conducts various activities in the realm of CBDM, the joint effort of multi-agency collaboration is very crucial for creating a disaster management framework. According to Paschalia et al. (2022), collaborative disaster training is essential for enhancing community-based disaster management by providing the necessary knowledge and skills required for effective disaster response. Research indicates that the implementation of community-based disaster risk reduction initiatives leads to a notable enhancement in the community's knowledge and skills in disaster prevention. Additionally, the efficiency of disaster simulation training, which combines instructional and simulation learning methods, has proven to enhance participants' understanding of communication, collaboration, and the application of incident command systems in disaster response (Gibson et al., 2023).

CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary

As provisioned by National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act 2017, the involvement of the APF, Nepal in Community-Based Disaster Management (CBDM) has provided valuable insights into its contributions, particularly in the areas of raising awareness, building capacity, and improving disaster response capabilities. Armed Police Force (APF), Nepal's proactive approach includes awareness programs to educate communities and school children about disaster risks and preparedness measures, conducting seminars, workshops, pamphlets, and social media. These initiatives, carried out 1260 times reaching 85,868 individuals, include a variety of disaster scenarios, significantly enhancing community understanding and reducing disaster vulnerabilities.

Moreover, APF, Nepal has been organizing multiple training sessions for community members, students, and other agencies, addressing community-based disaster issues such as collapsed structure search and rescue, swift water search and rescue, deep diving, firefighting, dead body management, medical first response, and rope rescue. Attended by 2669 participants, these sessions have proven effective in encouraging crucial skills for disaster response, including first aid, firefighting, and collapsed structure search and rescue.

The comprehensive first aid training has enabled individuals to offer quick assistance during disasters, while the firefighting sessions strengthen understanding of fire dynamics, methods of using tools, and equipment. Moreover, APF, Nepal has conducted collaborative training and drills with communities, schools, and other agencies, facilitating the exchange of resources and knowledge to empower local communities in CBDM. With a resource capacity that includes 2669 trained personnel in diverse rescue operations, the community's response capabilities have been found significantly strengthened. Particularly, the procedures for casualty evacuation have been seen as vital for minimizing casualties in road accidents, earthquakes, and landslides. The casualty evacuation training programs cover fundamental skills such as incident documentation, patient care, speedy treatment, and safe transport, all essential for stabilizing disaster victims.

Moreover, the involvement of APF, Nepal in search and rescue operations comprises training on structural triage, the INSARAG marking system, rescue tactics, handling construction materials, and load stabilization. These initiatives have remarkably increased resilience, self-efficiency, and knowledge, aiding in more effective management of major disasters.

In summary, the research highlights the efficiency of APF, Nepal's initiatives, as demonstrated by successful rescue missions in the disaster management fields. Through collaborations with local communities and other partner agencies, strong partnerships have been made, setting the ground for future coordination and collaboration, thus strengthening overall disaster readiness and response capabilities.

5.2 Findings

The study on the engagement of APF, Nepal in CBDM has found significant insights into its contribution to raising awareness, conducting capacity-building training, and enhancing its capability in various disaster response activities of the community and its personnel. The key findings are as follows:

5.2.1 Awareness Program: Linkage of Community and APF, Nepal

To enhance CBDM, APF, Nepal has been furnished a proactive approach and has conducted various awareness programs to educate the community and school children about disaster risks and preparedness measures which have significantly improved community understanding of disaster management practices. Likewise, by utilizing different teaching methods such as seminars, workshops, distribution of pamphlets, and using social media to disseminate information people are found to be educated.

The awareness programs that include cold waves, thunderbolts, windstorms, landslides, firefighting, monsoon response, water-induced disasters, and, basic introduction of disaster management are conducted 1260 times, to 85,868 people which helps to reduce community-based disaster risk. It is also found from the respondents that the involvement of the local people and school children is very high in disaster preparedness and response sessions.

5.2.2 Capacity Building and Simulation Activities Strengthening CBDM

APF, Nepal has organized numerous training sessions for school children and community members including a wide range of topics including CSSR, SWSS, Deep Diving, Fire Fighting,

DBM, MFR, and Rope Rescue. Feedback from the trainees has been found effective in responding more efficiently by developing essential skills among the participants.

Through capacity building, 2669 are being capacitated in various fields such as air-crash and mass casualty evacuation, firefighting, earthquake, CSSR, and first aid by training, simulations, and drills.

First aid training has given comprehensive knowledge by equipping them to provide quick and proper assistance during a disaster. Likewise, CSSR has provided operational noteworthy by demonstrating high proficiency in rescuing individuals trapped in collapsed structures.

Firefighting sessions have given important insight into using firefighting techniques and equipment through simulation and drills. The understanding of fire concept, fire behaviour techniques, and tools for suppression has been found well included in the training manual of APF, Nepal.

Likewise, as fire is one of the major disasters of Nepal, APF, Nepal is highly focused on training by conducting firefighting sessions for its personnel have been found very effective.

Moreover, the local people and other government agencies have found this training very important to learn methods and equipment for suppressing fire considering safety measures.

Joint exercises with community and school children have been instrumental in building capacity and APF, Nepal has facilitated in sharing of resources and knowledge to CBDM to empower the local community.

5.2.3 Resource Capability of APF, Nepal to Enhance CBDM

APF, Nepal has been engaging in various trainings such as CSSR, SWSS, deep diving, fire, fighting, dead body management, MFR, rope rescue, and cable car rescue have been trained to 2669 APF, Nepal personnel. These trainings have enhanced the community rescue and response operation actively.

The training on first aid has included basic incident reporting, checking the responsiveness of the patients, basic on-site treatment, and methods of carrying them safely up to the vehicles have been found significant in stabilizing the condition of the victim of disaster.

5.2.4 Search and Rescue Operations

To enhance CBDM APF, Nepal is engaging in search and rescue operations by conducting training on various subjects such as structural triage and INSARAG building marking system, soaring method, rescue strategies and techniques, construction materials, structure and damage type, search location techniques, lifting and stabilizing loads. These trainings have significantly improved resilience, self-efficacy, and knowledge, aiding in better coping with major earthquakes and landslides.

The study found that the training specially taught participants about safety measures, wearing full personal protective equipment how to make hitches and using of pulley to uplift the vehicle from the downward slope, how to operate water search and rescue tasks by using rubber boats and provide basic first aid treatments to the victim.

5.2.5 Casualty evacuation

APF, Nepal has been engaging in CBDM activities through different initiatives. Evacuation procedures conducted by the organization have been found to play a pivotal role in reducing casualties and safeguarding the welfare of the community in the event of natural disasters or unforeseen crises. During the study of the experience of APF, Nepal officers found that the APF, Nepal conducts training for its personnel for effective evacuation from vehicles during road accidents and from debris in earthquakes and landslides.

It is found that the APF, Nepal is well educated and has conducted practical knowledge on casualty evacuation as very important within the realm of disaster management as it facilitates the prompt and secure transportation of individuals in need to suitable healthcare establishments, consequently reducing both the loss of human lives and the extent of suffering. Similarly, the study shows that the skillful CSSR and MFR team plays a vital role in saving the life of people who conducts their operations focusing on the safety of the victims.

Overall, the rescue operation of vehicle accidents at Mugling, Kurintar has shown to be highly effective in employing the tools, techniques, and methods that have been learned before. Likewise, the example of the 2015 earthquake and the rescue of the live victim after 72 hours has been found one of the major strengths of APF, Nepal. Moreover, the conduction of various trainings, sessions, and drills with local community and school children have been found very effective. Joint exercise and conduction of training with other agencies have been found to

build good relations by knowing the capability of each other. And it is paving the way for future coordination and cooperation that will be effective during the disaster.

5.3 Conclusion

The involvement of the Armed Police Force (APF), Nepal in Community-Based Disaster Management (CBDM) has been remarkably effective, showing its significant contributions in various key domains in community-based disaster risk reduction that enhancing the legal provisions such as National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act 2017, and supports the Local Government Operation Act 2018. By implementing proactive awareness programs, APF, Nepal has conveyed knowledge to a wide range of the community, including students, concerning disaster risks and readiness measures. These initiatives, utilizing workshops, seminars, pamphlets, and social media platforms, have effectively reached 85,868 individuals, thereby substantially improving community awareness and mitigating community disaster risks.

Furthermore, APF, Nepal has been organizing comprehensive capacity-building training sessions, encompassing crucial areas such as collapsed structure search and rescue, swift water surface search, deep diving, firefighting, dead body management, medical first response, and rope rescue. These sessions have trained 2669 individuals, equipping them with the necessary skills for efficient disaster response. First aid training has provided participants with the essential knowledge to provide immediate aid during disasters, while firefighting training has enhanced their capability to handle fire-related incidents.

Moreover, the dedication of APF, Nepal to CBDM also involves collaborative exercises with community members and students, promoting the exchange of resources and knowledge that empowers local communities. The training given to APF, Nepal personnel has significantly enhanced their proficiency in various rescue operations, including triage, the INSARAG marking system, rescue tactics, and patients' stabilization. These endeavours have notably strengthened community resilience and the effectiveness of disaster response.

In conclusion, APF, Nepal's endeavors in CBDM have shown remarkable outcomes, characterized by successful rescue missions and improved disaster management protocols. Moreover, conducting disaster management training targeting to local community has shown its significant contribution to community disaster risk reduction. By collaborating with local communities and other organizations, strong partnerships have been made, laying the ground

for future coordination and collaboration, thereby enhancing overall disaster preparedness and response.

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APPENDIX A

Objective Tools of the Study

Research Question	Objective	Data Collection	Rational	Analysis
How is APF, Nepal, contributing to CBDM through its different initiatives?	To analysis of Community-Based Disaster Management (CBDM) initiatives carried out by APF, Nepal.	Secondary data and KII as primary data collection tool	Secondary data provided the foundation of the study and the KII provided in depth understanding about the subject and initiatives of APF, Nepal in CBDM domains.	Based on secondary data the understanding and knowledge of key informants in CBDM subjects have been analysed by Transcribing, coding, and thematic categorization of the interview.

APPENDIX B

Key Informant Interview Questions

A. Questions to Senior Officer of Armed Police Force, Nepal

1. For how many years have you working in CBDM fields?
2. How is your involvement in community engagement in the disaster management field? Can you explain, please?
3. Do you conduct awareness programs regularly or in time intervals?
4. Can you explain the preparedness of the local community and school children after getting basic insight into disaster management?
5. How effective do you think the training was in preparing you for real-world firefighting scenarios?
6. Can you share any specific incidents or exercises that you found particularly effective?
7. You said you are involved in road accident rescue operation. Can you share how you rescued the victim?
8. You said you have conducted practical drills and simulation exercises. Were they effective?
9. You have conducted and participated in collaborative disaster management training. What was the most positive aspect? Can you elaborate?

B. Questions Junior Officer of Armed Police Force, Nepal

1. For how many years have you working in CBDM fields? And how is your involvement in community engagement in the disaster management field?
2. In how many CBDM initiatives have you been involved during your entire service period? Can you share your experience of different training and awareness programs conducted in the community?
3. You said you have conducted practical drills and simulation exercises. Were they effective?
4. Can you share any specific incidents or exercises that you found particularly effective?

C. Questions to Non-Commissioned officer of Armed Police Force, Nepal

1. For how many years have you working in CBDM fields?
2. How do you explain the participation of the local community in disaster awareness sessions?

3. Had they previously known about the methods and techniques of using firefighting?
4. What insight have you given to local people during your disaster rescue session?
5. In how many CBDM initiatives have you been involved during your entire service period?
6. You said you were also engaged in earthquake rescue operations. Is there any special moment of rescuing a victim to share with me?

Questions to Local Representative of Ichhyakamana Village Municipality Chitwan

1. Have you been involved in any training and sessions of APF, Nepal?
2. If yes! What did you learn from those programs?
3. Which training program did you find important?
4. What knowledge have you learned from capacity development programs? Was it fruitful? Can you explain, please?
5. You said you have participated in medical first responder training, too. How and why, it is important to local people?
6. In your training manual, there is well well-structured collapsed structure search and rescue. As you are a trained disaster management officer how do you think it is effective?
7. What did you learn from the firefighting practical exercise?

Questions to Firefighting Officer of Juddha Barun Yantra, Kathmandu

1. Have you participated in any training or session conducted by APF, Nepal in the disaster field? If yes which training?
2. Was it effective? Can you share your experience of the training?
3. How do you think you are capable of suppression of basic fire? What did you learn exactly there?
4. How do you perceive APF, Nepal in the realm of disaster management?
5. How has the firefighting training influenced your approach in your daily duties?
6. Would you recommend this training program to other firefighters? Why or why not?
7. Do you think these kinds of collaborative trainings are fruitful? Why?